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The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and the Performance of the Employees

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of the ninety-eight municipal employees in Kitaotao who were randomly chosen for the two semesters of the calendar year 2023. Specifically, the following problems were presented in the study: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description? What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of capability building or trainings attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers? What is the employees' performance level in the Municipality of Kitaotao? Is there a significant relationship between the employees' job satisfaction level and their performance as municipal employees when grouped according to capability building or trainings attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers? Is there a significant difference in municipal employees' performance when grouped according to age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description? The data gathered were summarized using frequency counts, percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and Analysis of Variance. This study revealed that majority of the employees were in their fifties, female, married, with average monthly salary, college graduates, and administrative aides. They elicited a satisfactory level of job satisfaction and were very satisfactory in their job performances. Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between their level of job satisfaction and their performance as municipal employees. Also, no significant differences were found in the job performance of the employees when they were grouped according to age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description. This study confirmed that job satisfaction did not affect the performance of the municipal employees. Moreover, the municipal employees were generally satisfied and performed well with their jobs as what is expected of them regardless of age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, performance, municipal employee*

Introduction

Municipal employees are the heart of local government units (LGUs). There is a general understanding that an organization's overall productivity and success depend on its employees' effective and efficient performance, and that better performance depends on the employees' job satisfaction. Municipal heads and human resource managers should continue cultivating satisfied and good workforce values among municipal employees. Thus, government policies and programs should continue to motivate and encourage more employees to be committed to their profession.

Job satisfaction refers to how individuals feel about their jobs, encompassing their contentment or discontentment with their work. It can also reflect good treatment and be an indicator of emotional well-being. It concerns several attitudes, including job characteristics, compensation and benefits, status, social security, advancement opportunities, technological challenges, and respect. Work, pay, promotion, supervision, and co-workers are the most widely used job satisfaction factors.

Productive job performance is often confused with "effort," which refers to energy expended. It is the accomplishment of an employee's or manager's assigned duties and the outcomes produced by performing a particular task or activity within a set time frame. Managing performance is done with the employees because it gives an advantage to the employees, the manager, and the organization. It is done collaboratively. A yearly performance evaluation based on job satisfaction is one of the things to do. Most effective production methods. Influence morale. It could justify reward decisions such as promotions, merits, and other rewards. This also allows both the supervisors and subordinates to develop a plan for correcting any deficiencies that the appraisal might have reinforced, and the feedback clarifies the employee's job expectations held by their specific supervisors. Performance appraisal helps evaluate the individual's share relative to the team's contribution to achieving the organization's goal (Angeles et al., 2015).

Municipal government employees are generally committed to and accountable for their jobs. Employee involvement is a crucial indicator of productivity and engagement, and performance will grow as employees become more efficient as long as they feel appreciated and pleased at work. Thus, awareness of how government staff become pleased and devoted to their jobs and how different elements can be a factor in the level of dedication is critical to improving their performance (De Leon et al., 2022).

Municipal government employees are generally committed to and accountable for their jobs. Employee involvement is a crucial indicator of productivity and engagement, and performance will grow as employees become more efficient as long as they feel appreciated and pleased at work. Thus, awareness of how government staff become pleased and devoted to their jobs and how different elements can be a factor in the level of dedication is critical to improving their performance (De Leon et al., 2022).

The researcher intended to know the relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of municipal employees. Determining the factors contributing to employee satisfaction that significantly affect their performance was the primary concern of this study. A local study has not determined whether municipal employees are satisfied with their jobs. The goal of this study was to see if these factors affected their job performance.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees for the year 2022. This study's main objective was to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description?
2. What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers?
3. What is the employees' performance level in the Municipality of Kitaotao?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the employees' job satisfaction level and their performance as municipal employees when grouped according to capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers?
5. Is there a significant difference in municipal employees' performance when grouped according to age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description?

Methodology

Research Design

The study applied the descriptive-correlational design. This technique aimed at determining whether or not two or more variables were connected. Descriptive design was concerned with the conditions of the prevailing practices or processes that develop. This technique was adopted to describe the current behavior or features of the population. Data collection and tabulation were only one part of the descriptive research process. It entails several criteria in determining the meaning and relevance of the information provided. On the other hand, correlational design was used to determine whether one or more variables have a relationship. Using this design, the relationship between course specialization and job satisfaction would be determined.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the ninety-eight (98) permanent and casual employees from the different offices of the Local Government Unit of Kitaotao, Bukidnon, for the calendar year 2022.

This study utilized a stratified random sampling method. The offices of the municipal employees would serve as strata, and the sample was composed of randomly selected individuals from each stratum.

The researcher used Slovin's formula by Robert Slovin 1960 to compute the sample size, with confidence level and margin of error of 95% and 5%, respectively. With fifteen (15) offices, one hundred twenty-nine (129) permanent and casual employees will serve as the population for this study, and using Slovin's formula, the sample size to be obtained was ninety-eight (98). The complete list of the strata is shown in Table 1, with the number of participants selected from each office. The number of populations was obtained from the Human Resource Management Office (HRMO) of LGU-Kitaotao, Bukidnon.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by office

<i>Strata (Office)</i>	<i>Permanent</i>		<i>Casual</i>		<i>Calculated Sample Size</i>
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	
Municipal Agriculture Office	4	5			9
Municipal Accounting Office	1	2	1		4
Municipal Treasurer's Office	4	1		2	7
Municipal Assessor's Office	1	2			3
Municipal Social Welfare & Development Office	1	1			2
Municipal Mayor's Office		5	6	2	13
Human Resource Management Office	2		1	2	5
Municipal Disaster & Risk Reduction Management Office	1			1	2
Municipal Budget Office	1		1	1	3
Municipal Planning & Development Office		4		2	6
Municipal Engineering Office	2	1	1	4	8
Municipal Heath Office	1	11	1	8	21
Local Civil Registrar's Office				1	1
Sangguniang Bayan Office		2	7	2	11
General Services Office	2			1	3
Total	20	34	18	26	98

Instrument

The study used a self-made questionnaire composed of three (3) parts.

The first part of the questionnaire was about the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description.

The second part was the variables and indicators that would measure the relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of the employees. The items were developed to be rated on a five-point Likert rating scale (5-Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3- Neutral, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly Disagree) with higher scores indicating satisfaction and lesser scores indicating that employees were not satisfied in their job.

The last part was the variable that measured the performance of the respondents. This refers to the respondents' rating in their IPCR for the two semesters of the calendar year 2022.

Administration of Research Instrument

Through a letter, the researcher formally asked permission to conduct the study first from the office of the municipal mayor of LGU-Kitaotao, Bukidnon.

The researcher submitted a letter request to the head of the LGU-Kitaotao HR office to ask permission to obtain the list of permanent and casual employees for the calendar year 2022.

The researcher solved the sample size using Slovin's formula after obtaining the list and names of permanent and casual employees.

The researcher conducted a pilot test to select respondents via stratified random sampling.

The questionnaire attained above 70 of Cronbach's Alpha, so the researcher then administered the questionnaire herself to the respondents through office-to-office visitation.

Consent from the respondents was asked. The researcher explained the purpose of the survey and ensured the utmost privacy and confidentiality of the information gathered by answering the questionnaire.

Validity of the Instrument

The pilot testing phase of the instrument was administered to a small population group. The researcher launched a sample of 30 questionnaires to 30 who were not part of this study to determine the validity of the instruments. The pilot-testing phase is also a way to measure and establish the accuracy and reliability of the study's questionnaire by determining its consistency via Cronbach's Alpha. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient was .899, which means it passed the test and ensured the statements' comprehensibility, appropriateness, and validity.

Scoring Procedure

Descriptive statistics were used in this study to analyze the data gathered through the self-made questionnaire and to summarize the collected data quantitatively. From the Likert-type scale responses, the respondents' mean scores were computed for interpretation using an adapted table of ranges from the advanced concepts by Rensis Likert (1968), as shown in Table 2, and exact limits as introduced by L.R. (1983 Rev. Ed).

Table 2. A. *On the Level of Job Satisfaction*

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Qualifying Statement</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree	5 out of 5 instances
4	3.40-4.19	Agree	4 out of 5 instances
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral	3 out of 5 instances
2	1.80-2.59	Disagree	2 out of 5 instances
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree	1 out of 5 instances

B. For the performance rating of the respondents based on the average rating of their IPCR for the two (2) consecutive semesters, January to June 2022 and July to December 2022, a five-point scale was used.

Table 3. B. *On the Level of Performance*

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range of Performance</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
5	4.5 – 5.0	Outstanding
4	3.5 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory
3	2.5 – 3.499	Satisfactory
2	1.55 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory
1	1.0 – 1.499	Poor

Procedure

The researcher distributed the self-made research questionnaire to the respondents and explained the purpose of the study. Respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaire. The researcher exclusively answered any queries by the respondents. The data were encoded and collated, and only the respondents designated were projected in the data.

Data Analysis

For the analysis of data, the following statistical tools were used:

Frequency counts and percentage distribution were applied to determine the demographic profile of the respondents.

Mean, and standard deviation were utilized to determine the employees' job satisfaction level.

Frequency counts and percentage distribution were used to determine the employees' performance levels in Kitaotao, Bukidnon.

Pearson's *r* was used to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and their performance as municipal employees.

ANOVA, or analysis of variance, was employed to determine the difference between municipal employees' performance when grouped according to their age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, and job description.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the presentation of findings, the analysis of every answer to the problem statement, and the interpretation of data with support from the Review of Related Literature.

The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, job description; the level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, relationship with co-workers and others were presented in this section.

Table 4 provides the answer to the problem, "What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age?"

Table 4. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age*

Age	<i>f</i>	%
26 – 30 Years Old	9	9.2
31 – 35 Years Old	8	8.2
36 – 40 Years Old	13	13.3
41 – 45 Years Old	14	14.3
46 – 50 Years Old	12	12.2
51 Years Old and Above	41	41.8
Total	98	100

As can be gleaned in Table 4, most employees were 51 years old and above, with the highest percentage of 41.8%. Others were 41 - 45 years old, comprised 14.3%, 36 - 40 years old with 13.3%, and 46 – 50 with 12.2%, respectively. This implied that the age bracket of the majority of the municipal employees belong to Generation X, meaning they are seasoned employees who are mature enough to handle the task/job assigned to them.

Generation X is best described as having a better education than previous generations. They value work-life balance and professional development, work well collaboratively, flexible, independently, autonomously, and tech-savvy (Buffet, 2022), which connotes that employees are happier and with greater confidence when they come to work that, in turn, translates into higher overall job satisfaction, employee performance, productivity, and overall morale.

The findings of Nufable's (2017) in her study supported the result that 51 years old and above have higher performance compared to employees who are 30 years and below, 31 to 40 years old, and 41 to 50 years. This was evidenced by the consistent, very satisfactory performance of the municipal employees in Kitaotao, Bukidnon, for two consecutive semesters in 2022.

Table 5 indicates the outcome of the problem: "What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex?"

Table 5. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex*

Sex	<i>f</i>	%
Male	38	38.8
Female	60	61.2
Total	98	100

It was revealed in Table 5 that most municipal employees were female, with 61.2% of females dominating the number of male

respondents in the study, which was only 38.8%.

The result of this study can be associated with the high rating of employee performance, which was described as very satisfactory since most of the employees were female.

The result parallels the study that women have made great strides in education and the utilization of that education in the workforce over the past sixty years. More women than ever are receiving higher education, in numbers that are even surpassing that of men. Women in higher roles lead to greater profitability and success (Ziman, 2013). This is the reason why the female outnumbered the male respondents. As per the study, a higher percentage of women in the workplace provides better job satisfaction, enhances organizational dedication, more meaningful work, and less burn-out.

Findings of the study on the factors associated with the job performance of municipal employees in Miagao: Basis for human resource policy recommendation also supported the result of the study, which revealed that female employees performed better than males (Nufable, 2017).

Presented in Table 6 was the answer to the problem, “What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of marital status?”

Table 6. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of marital status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Single	6	6.1
Married	88	89.8
Separated	3	3.1
Widow	1	1
Widower	0	0
Others	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 6 revealed that most municipal employees were married, comprising 89.8%. Few were single, 6.1%, and 3.1% were separated.

It can be noted that the result of this study asserted that married employees dominated in LGU-Kitaotao, and this could be associated with the reason why their performance level was rated very satisfactory, as stressed by the findings of the studies below. It was established that marital status influenced job satisfaction where the married were much happier than the single (Kemunto et al., 2018).

The result of the study can be correlated with the study evaluating the impact of marital status on employees' job performance, which showed a significant positive relationship between marital status and job performance. Information about this investigation is advantageous for Human Resource Managers to prefer employees toward job activity and job satisfaction after marriage (Aslam et al., 2020).

Findings of the study on the factors associated with the job performance of municipal employees in Miagao: Basis for human resource policy recommendation showed that married employees have a higher level of performance compared to single, widowed, and separated ones (Nufable, 2017).

Reflected in Table 7 was the answer to the problem, “What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly salary?”

Table 7. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly salary*

<i>Monthly Salary</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
10,000 – 15,000	55	56.1
16,000 - 20,000	7	7.1
21,000 - 25,000	12	12.3
26,000 - 30,000	5	5.1
31,000 - 35,000	7	7.1
36,000 - 40,000	1	1
41,000 - 45,000	3	3.1
Others	8	8.2
Total	98	100

There were 55 municipal employees, or 56.1%, receiving a monthly salary of 10,000 – 15,000, and most of them were casual employees, for they are paid a daily wage rate, and some were permanent employees with a job description of administrative aides. Others had a monthly salary of 21,000 – 25,000, which comprised 12.3%. In contrast, the highest monthly salary is 45,000 and above, with 8.2% for the heads of offices and their next in ranks.

The result implied that most respondent employees receive an average monthly salary. However, still, they performed very well with the tasks/jobs assigned to them, as backed up by their IPCR ratings with descriptive equivalent of very satisfactory. This is so because they are also entitled to some benefits and bonuses the LGU provides that motivate them to work harder.

A study on performance evaluation on salary showed that the employee's salary could be significantly and negatively influenced by performance evaluation, gender, education, and performance evaluation moderated by gender. In contrast, the position, experience, and performance evaluation moderated by position, education, and experience do not affect the salary (Shamki, 2019).

Table 8 portrays the result of the problem: "What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment?"

Table 8. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
AB Graduate	10	10.2
BS Agriculture Graduate	10	10.2
BS Engineering Graduate	5	5.1
BSBA Graduate	4	4.1
BS Accounting Graduate	4	4.1
BS Nursing Graduate	1	1
BS Information Technology Graduate	3	3.1
Others	61	62.2
Total	98	100

Table 8 revealed that most of the municipal employees were college graduates and bachelor's degree holders, which implies that they are most qualified for the jobs in their respective offices. Moreover, the longer they stay in the LGU, the more they will be skillful with their job, as this becomes a daily routine for them, thus contributing to very satisfactory performance.

A college degree is highly beneficial for higher pay, job security, and other societal benefits that can lead to a comfortable and fulfilling life. Investing in a post-secondary credential almost always pays off, as it provides professional versatility and opens up many job opportunities across different fields. Additionally, a degree allows for continued growth and skill development throughout one's career. In summary, obtaining a college degree provides financial stability and longevity in one's profession (Bouchrika, 2022).

Presented in Table 9 was the answer to the problem, "What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job description?"

Table 9. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job description*

<i>Job Description</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Accounting Work	3	3
Administrative Aide	52	52.5
Assessor/Tax Mapper	1	1
Agricultural Extension Worker	9	9.1
Clerical Work	2	3
Engineering Work	2	2
Health Worker	8	8.1
Others	21	21.3
Total	98	100

The results revealed that most of the employees in LGU-Kitaotao have a job description of administrative aide with the highest percentage of 52.5%. This is so because all the casual employees' job descriptions were uniform as administrative aides and comprised almost one-half of the total respondents. In addition, there are some permanent employees also with the same job description.

It can be deduced from the result of this study that a clear job description can help employees improve employee performance because employees have a direction toward their primary task and function at work. A less clear job description will result in an employee not knowing his duties and responsibilities. This can result in the work going wrong. A clear and specified job description helps in improving organizational justice and employee performance while establishing a culture of justice will positively lead to better employee performance and enhance the explanation of the relationship between job description and employee performance. Decision-makers are recommended to create clear job descriptions and to improve organizational justice to increase employee performance in the public sector (Rawas & Jantan, 2022).

The survey results in Table 10 answer the question, "What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of capability building or training attended?" The table provides each indicator's average and standard deviation, along with a qualitative description and scale for interpreting the numbers.

Results revealed that the indicator "The LGU implements and supports the employees in their capability training financially and morally" obtained the highest mean score of 4.88 with the qualitative description of "very satisfied." The LGU's provision of financial and moral support has satisfied the employees' capabilities. Building and training. For example, the Agricultural Extension Workers will attend an Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Training at DA-Regional Field Office 10 in Cagayan de Oro City; the LGU provided the traveling expenses and per diems of the participants for that particular training.

Table 10. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of capability building/trainings attended

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The LGU implements and supports the employees in their capability trainings financially and morally.	4.88	0.359	Very Satisfied
The LGU provides us with effective and efficient trainings relevant to our present job.	4.45	0.558	Very Satisfied
The LGU provides us with updated trainings.	4.41	0.589	Very Satisfied
The LGU implements equal participation of employees in capability trainings regardless of status and position.	4.02	0.592	Satisfied
The LGU provides us with regular trainings.	3.93	0.677	Satisfied
Overall	4.34	0.407	Very Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

The indicator with the lowest mean score was The LGU provides us with regular training with a mean of 3.93, indicating that employees are less satisfied with the frequency of the training offered by the LGU. In general, the employees were delighted in capability building/training attended, with its overall mean of 4.34 indicating that they are delighted with the capability building/training attended.

Researchers concluded that employee training positively impacts job satisfaction, such as increasing productivity, where employers and employees can contribute to their performance through employee training and share the benefits from training (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013).

Table 11 shows the result of the problem “What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of promotion opportunities?” The mean and standard deviation are also presented, along with the score and scale interpretation, corresponding qualitative descriptions, and qualifying statements.

Table 11. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of promotion opportunities

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The LGU helps the employees increase their promotion opportunities according to their length of service.	4.68	0.602	Very Satisfied
Promotion is based on merit, seniority and fitness.	4.29	0.658	Very Satisfied
Promotion opportunities are equally given to the employees for those who are qualified in the applied position.	4.05	0.598	Satisfied
There are many promotion opportunities in the LGU when you are willing to be promoted in accordance with your educational attainment and other skills.	3.74	0.58	Satisfied
The LGU helps and supports the employees in promotion opportunities by sending them for masteral studies.	3.32	0.529	Neutral
Overall	4.02	0.419	Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

The highest mean score was obtained for indicator 4: "The LGU helps the employees increase their promotion opportunities according to their length of service." The employees rated this indicator as "Very Satisfied," with the highest mean score of 4.68. The second-highest mean score was obtained for Indicator 1, which states, "Promotion is based on merit, seniority, and fitness." The employees also rated this indicator as "Very Satisfied," with a mean of 4.29. Indicator 2, which states that "Promotion opportunities are equally given to the employees who are qualified in the applied position," was rated as "Satisfied" with a mean of 4.05. Indicator 5, which states that "There are many promotion opportunities in the LGU when you are willing to be promoted by your educational attainment and other skills," was rated as "Satisfied" with a mean of 3.74. Indicator 3 states that "The LGU helps and supports the employees in promotion opportunities by sending them for master studies," rated as "Neutral" with the lowest mean of 3.32.

Overall, the employees were rated as "Satisfied" with a mean of 4.02 with their level of job satisfaction in terms of promotion opportunities meaning the employees were satisfied in terms of promotion opportunities. The LGU needs to support employees who wish to pursue graduate or master studies, as this area received the lowest ratings. Employees considered the support provided by the LGU as neutral, indicating dissatisfaction with the level of assistance offered in pursuing higher education. This support is essential for their career growth and promotion to higher positions. Healthy competition for promotion motivates employees to improve their performance and creates job stability. The HR department should give this enough attention because although the employees were satisfied, the overall mean is lower than other variable indicators of job satisfaction. Yaseen (2013) found that pay, recognition, promotion opportunities and meaningful work are essential factors of compensation management that directly affect job satisfaction among doctors who were the study's respondents.

Table 12 indicates the answer to the problem “What is the employees’ job satisfaction level in terms of security of tenure?”

As shown in Table 12, employees were most satisfied with the indicator "We are enjoying the security of tenure if we are CSC eligible," with the highest mean of 4.90, followed by We do not experience unjust termination of employment with the mean of 4.76. LGU

protects us against unjust termination from employment with its mean of 4.53. Both gained a descriptive equivalent of "very satisfied."

Table 12. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of security of tenure

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
We are enjoying security of tenure if we are CSC eligible.	4.9	0.336	Very Satisfied
We don't experience unjust termination of employment.	4.76	0.499	Very Satisfied
LGU protects us against unjustly termination from employment.	4.53	0.522	Very Satisfied
LGU makes sure that we are protected from oppressive termination from employment.	4.44	0.576	Very Satisfied
LGU makes sure that we are secure with our jobs regardless of our political status and political color.	3.68	0.585	Satisfied
Overall	4.46	0.365	Very Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

The indicator "LGU makes sure that we are secure with our jobs regardless of our political status and political color," with a mean of 3.68, received the lowest mean, indicating that employees are satisfied but not as much as other indicators. This suggests that some concerns regarding political status and color may affect job security. Overall, the employees were delighted in terms of security of tenure, with an overall mean of 4.46.

The Weberian Model of Bureaucracy emphasizes the need for employees to have a security of tenure to ensure their maximum security in the organization. Also, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs placed security or safety next to physical needs. Security needs refer to the things that help employees to secure themselves from danger of losing health, wealth, or job (Abdurahman, 2020).

Table 13 illustrates the outcome of the problem: "What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of hiring process and procedure?"

Table 13. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of hiring process and procedure

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Hiring process and procedure is fast and published in the bulletin board and facebook for transparency purposes.	4.86	0.38	Very Satisfied
Hiring process and procedure is based on merits and HR guidelines.	4.28	0.533	Very Satisfied
Hiring process and procedure implement fairness and equality.	3.66	0.591	Satisfied
There are procedures in the hiring process that are irrelevant and outdated.	2.62	0.547	Neutral
There are procedures in the hiring process that are inconvenient inconsistent with the hiring guidelines.	2.6	0.57	Neutral
Overall	3.6	0.3	Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

As revealed in Table 13, the indicators "Hiring process and procedure is fast and published in the bulletin board and Facebook for transparency purposes" with a mean of 4.86 and "Hiring process and procedure is based on merits and HR guidelines" with a mean of 4.28 obtained the first two highest scores which indicate that the municipal employees were delighted in the hiring process and procedure. The overall mean of the indicators is 3.60, which falls under the satisfied category. The employees were delighted with the speed and transparency of the hiring process and procedure, as indicated by the mean score of 4.86 for indicator 3.

Overall, the employees were satisfied with the hiring process and procedure, with a mean of 3.60, although indicators were rated neutral. However, the mean score is lower compared to other variables. This implies that some employees were unsatisfied with the hiring process and procedure, especially in the "hiring process implement fairness and equality." The HR Department should give this attention for this significantly affect the employees' job satisfaction, as revealed in this study's result.

The result of this study conformed with the result of Park (2021), which showed that there is little doubt that this study was significant and relevant to the relationship between fair hiring policy and worker job satisfaction, indicating that an organization that practices a fair hiring policy positively affects employee job satisfaction.

Table 14 shows the result of the problem "What is the employees' job satisfaction level in terms of healthy working environment?"

Table 14. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of healthy working environment.

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I grow professionally with my working environment.	4.89	0.317	Very Satisfied
My boss is very understanding and helpful.	4.21	0.707	Very Satisfied
I worked things which are not part of my job description in order to meet deadlines.	3.57	0.574	Satisfied
I work beyond what I am paid for.	3.13	0.568	Neutral

Workload is very heavy.	3.11	0.348	Neutral
Overall	3.78	0.24	Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

The indicators used in this table include growth opportunities, the boss's supportiveness, workload, working beyond pay, and doing things beyond the job description. The results showed that employees are delighted with the opportunities for growth in their working environment, with a mean of 4.89. They also reported high satisfaction levels with their boss's supportiveness, with a mean of 4.21. However, the overall rating was only satisfied with the mean of 3.78 with their working environment, indicating areas that could be improved. The employees reported being satisfied with a mean of 3.57 with their ability to work on tasks beyond their job description to meet deadlines, but neutral with a mean of 3.13 about working beyond what they are paid for and a heavy workload mean of 3.11.

Overall, the employees were satisfied with their working environment. However, there is room for improvement in workload and compensation for work beyond their job description. A study by Loquias and Sana (2013) concludes that the factors significantly associated with job satisfaction are the work-environment variables, perceived institutional support, and stress. These suggest that educational leaders can improve job satisfaction by altering the organizational environment and hopefully indirectly alter or influence the inner state of the individuals that make up the organization.

Table 15 presents the answer to the problem “What is the employees’ job satisfaction level in terms of relationship with co-workers?”

Table 15 revealed that the indicators "We work as a team in order to achieve our common goal" with a mean of 4.50 and "We help each other and work as a team in order to achieve our goals in the office" with a mean of 4.36 gained the first two highest scores which indicate that they were delighted in their relationship with their co-workers. The indicator "My co-workers are very loving, caring and understanding," with a mean score of 3.77, gained the lowest mean, which indicates satisfied employees. The employees were generally satisfied with their work relationships with co-workers, with an overall mean of 4.12.

Table 15. Level of job satisfaction of the municipal employees in terms of relationship with co-workers

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
We work as a team in order to achieve our common goal.	4.5	0.579	Very Satisfied
We help each other and work as a team in order to achieve our goals in the office.	4.36	0.579	Very Satisfied
Our boss is very supportive for our educational growth.	4.1	0.78	Satisfied
My co-workers are very helpful in all our endeavors.	3.87	0.652	Satisfied
My co-workers are very loving, caring and understanding.	3.77	0.623	Satisfied
Overall	4.12	0.454	Satisfied

Scale: 4.20–5.00 – Strongly Agree | 3.40–4.19 – Agree | 2.60–3.39 – Neutral | 1.80–2.59 – Disagree | 1.00–1.79 – Strongly Disagree

The result of the study obeyed the findings of Chadi and Hetschko (2018), who highlighted the essential role of job satisfaction in improving performance. A company can push sellers to sell more, but sellers need to be more happy at work to be motivated to sell to the best of their ability. The second major category of high-quality workplace relationships involves peer relationships, equivalent relationships between similar-status peers in the organization.

Table 16 shows the answer to the problem “What is the employees’ performance level in the Municipality of Kitaotao?”

Table 16. Level of performance of the municipal employees in the Municipality of Kitaotao

Rating	Range	f	%
5	4.5 – 5.0	0	0
4	3.5 – 4.499	97	99
3	2.5 – 3.499	1	1
2	1.5 – 2.499	0	0
1	1.0 – 1.499	0	0
Total		98	100

It also provides a rating system with a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 is the highest rating, and 1 is the lowest. The table also provides a range for each rating, with the corresponding percentage of employees who received that rating.

As shown in Table 16, almost all employees received performance ratings between 3.5 – 4.499, with a very high percentage of 99% which means that these employees were very satisfactory in their work performances.

The results implied that the municipal employees performed well regardless of their status as permanent or casual employees, as evidenced by the very satisfactory rating of their IPCR for the two consecutive semesters of the calendar year 2022.

The very satisfactory level of the job performance of the municipal employees could be attributed to the following reasons: they felt that their present salaries were commensurate to the tasks assigned to them, they were pleased with their bonuses and other incentives offered periodically, as well as allowances, assistance and benefits extended from the LGU.

The result of the study also conformed with the recent study conducted in the school district in Cotabato City, Philippines concludes that the teachers of the Division of Cotabato City display a high level of performance-related skills, abilities, initiatives, and productivity, exceeding requirements in many of the area of work performance (Usop et al., 2013).

Table 17 presents the answer to the problem "Is there a significant relationship between the employees' job satisfaction level and their performance as municipal employees when they are grouped according to capability building or training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedures, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers?" The table also shows the correlation coefficient (r) and the p -value for each variable.

Table 17. *Test of significant relationship between the level of job satisfaction of the respondents and their performance as municipal employees*

Variable	r	P - value
Capability Building/Training Attended	0.066	0.518
Promotion Opportunities	-0.004	0.969
Security of Tenure	0.095	0.353
Hiring Process and Procedure	-0.001	0.989
Healthy Working Environment	0.092	0.367
Relationship with Co-Workers	0.153	0.132

When analyzing the relationship between variables and employee performance, a positive correlation coefficient implies a positive relationship, while a negative correlation coefficient implies a negative relationship. A p -value below 0.05 is considered statistically significant, indicating a significant relationship between the variable and employee performance.

Table 17 showed a statistically significant positive relationship between employee performance and the "Security of Tenure" variable, as seen by a correlation coefficient of 0.095 and a p -value of 0.353.

However, the other variables, including Capability Building/Training Attended, Promotion Opportunities, Hiring Process and Procedure, Healthy Working Environment, and Relationship with Co-Workers, did not show statistically significant relationships with employee performance as their p -values are all greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the job satisfaction of the employees and their performance as municipal employees when they are grouped according to capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment and relationship with co-workers is accepted.

In general, the result showed that although the satisfaction level of the municipal employees about their performance as municipal employees was only found to be statistically significantly positive on the "security of tenure" variable, the municipal employees still performed very well in their jobs with descriptive equivalent of very satisfactory in their IPCR for the two consecutive semesters in 2022. This can be associated with the bonuses and other incentives the LGU gives to all employees regardless of status. It motivated the employees to work harder and become more productive, contributing to satisfactory performance ratings. A recent study on the sports industry found a positive but weak correlation between job satisfaction and performance. Using a scale, the study's authors, Ertekin and Avunduk (2021), measured several sub-dimensions of job satisfaction and performance.

Table 18 shows the answer to the problem, "Is there a significant difference in municipal employee's performance when grouped according to age?"

Table 18. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to age*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p -value
Between Groups	0.24	35	0.007	0.566	0.964
Within Groups	0.75	62	0.012		
Total	0.99	97			

Table 18 revealed no significant difference in the employees' IPCR ratings when the respondents are grouped according to age with F equal to .566 and p -value of .964. The results mean the employees' IPCR ratings were statistically the same across all age groups.

This implied that regardless of age, whether they belong to millennials, generation Z, or Generation X, the municipal employees performed very well in their respective jobs. As workers grow older, they initially tend to be slightly more satisfied with their jobs, and they lower their expectations to more realistic levels and adjust themselves better to their work situations.

Results of the study on the relationships between age, work experience, cognition, and workability in older employees in the heavy industry supported the result of this study that there was no correlation between a worker's age and cognitive function or workability. In addition, there was no significant correlation between workability and age or number of years in service. Although it cannot be said

that older workers with more experience always have a higher workability (Chung et al., 2015)

Table 19 illustrates the output of the problem: “Is there a significant difference in municipal employees’ performance when grouped according to sex?”

As shown in Table 19, the IPCR of employees who are male with a mean of 2.03 and female with a mean of 2.00 have no significant difference with t equal to 1.233 and p -value of .220. The results indicate that male and female employees have statistically the same ratings in their IPCR.

Table 19. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to sex*

Sex	Mean	t	p -value
Male	2.03	1.233	0.22
Female	2.00		

It is very clear that regardless of sex, the municipal employees really did their job diligently, as proven by the very satisfactory ratings in their IPCR.

A recent study in Pakistan examined the correlation between demographic characteristics and job performance. The study found that gender did not significantly impact job performance, indicating that innovation did not improve job performance while being moderated by gender. Additionally, the study revealed a negative beta value, suggesting that gender could have an indirect and direct inverse moderating effect on the relationship between innovation and performance. These findings support the results of the study.

Table 20 presents the result of the problem: “Is there a significant difference in municipal employees’ performance when grouped according to marital status?”

Table 20. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to marital status*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p -value
Between Groups	0.001	3	0	0.041	0.989
Within Groups	0.989	94	0.011		
Total	0.99	97			

As shown in Table 20, the IPCR ratings of the employees have no significant difference when they are grouped according to their marital status, with F equal to .041.

The results implied that regardless of the employee's marital status, whether they are single, married, separated, or widowed, they have the same IPCR ratings of very satisfactory, meaning they performed very well in the job assigned to them.

A study on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in the sports industry revealed that there was no significant difference according to the participant's marital status and the duration of their work (Ertekin & Avunduk, 2021), which conformed with the result of this study.

Table 21 presents the answer to the problem: “Is there a significant difference in the municipal employees’ performance when grouped according to salary?”

Table 21. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to salary*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P -value
Between Groups	0.073	7	0.01	1.026	0.419
Within Groups	0.917	90	0.01		
Total	0.99	97			

As revealed in Table 21, the municipal employees' IPCR ratings for the two consecutive semesters in 2022 have no significant difference when grouped according to salary, with an F equal to 1.026 and p -value of .419. This implied that the municipal employees had an average salary of 10,000 to 15,000. The municipal employees having higher salaries, like the head of offices, have the same very satisfactory ratings in their IPCR, meaning even though some of the employees have lower salaries, they still perform very well in their respective jobs, like those receiving higher salaries.

A study on performance evaluation on salary showed that the employee's salary could be significantly and negatively influenced by performance evaluation, gender, education, and performance evaluation moderated by gender, while the position, experience, performance evaluation moderated by position, education, and experience do not affect the salary (Shamki, 2019).

Table 22 demonstrates the result of the problem: “Is there a significant difference in municipal employees' performance when grouped according to their educational attainment?”

Table 22. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to their educational attainment*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Between Groups	0.09	7	0.013	1.283	0.268
Within Groups	0.9	90	0.01		
Total	0.99	97			

Table 22 shows that the IPCR ratings of the municipal employees have no significant difference when grouped according to their educational attainment, with F equal to 1.283 and p – the value of .268.

The results indicated that their IPCR ratings were statistically the same regardless of their educational attainment, which implies that professionals or not, the municipal did exemplary performance with the job assigned to them.

The result of this study was supported by the study on the relationship between educational attainment and job performance of workers among the six sectors of the business process outsourcing industry in Metro Manila, which showed that educational attainment and job performance had an indirect but weak relationship and statistically significant relationship. Therefore educational attainment does not have a significant relationship with job performance among the six business process outsourcing industry (Gan et al., 2012).

Table 23 presents the answer to the problem: “Is there a significant difference in municipal employees' performance when grouped according to their job description?”

Table 23. *Test of significant difference on the performance of municipal employees when they are grouped according to their job description*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Between Groups	0.09	7	0.013	1.283	0.268
Within Groups	0.9	90	0.01		
Total	0.99	97			

Table 23 revealed that the municipal employees' IPCR ratings have no significant difference when grouped according to their job description, with F equal to 1.283 and a p-value of .268.

The results revealed further that their IPCR ratings are the same regardless of their job description, which means that the municipal employees work hard as to what is the description of their job upon appointment.

This was supported by the study on factors associated with the job performance of municipal employees in Miagao: basis for human resource policy recommendation, wherein the findings were that no significant differences were found in the job performance of the employees when they were grouped according to the personal related factors as their age, sex, years in service and job status/position (Nufable, 2017).

The results of tables 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, and 23 provided evidence to accept the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in municipal employees' performance when grouped according to their profile. This implies that regardless of their age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description, the municipal employees of Kitaotao, Bukidnon performed very well in their assigned tasks/jobs, as proven by the very satisfactory ratings in their IPCR for the 2 consecutive semesters in 2022.

The municipal employees of Kitaotao were composed of diverse or complex personalities. They differ in their demographic profile as to age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description.

Likewise, they differ in their level of satisfaction as to capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, working environment, and relationship with their co-workers.

However, in totality, the municipal employees in Kitaotao, Bukidnon showed the same level of performance, which was rated very satisfactory as shown in their IPCR for two consecutive semesters for the calendar year 2022, regardless of their demographic profile as well as their level of satisfaction across all the variable indicators which implied that in general, the employees in the Municipality of Kitaotao work hand in hand for the attainment of the LGUs goal of priority which was productivity.

This conformed with the introductory statements of this study, which states that the municipal employees are considered the heart of the LGUs, for the organization's overall productivity and success depend on the employees' effective and efficient performance.

Conclusions

Given these findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

Most municipal employees were in their fifties, female, and married, with average monthly salaries, primarily professionals and administrative aides.

The municipal employees of Kitaotao, Bukidnon elicited a satisfactory level of job satisfaction across all the variable indicators such as capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers, which means that they satisfied and happy with their job.

The municipal employees had a very satisfactory job performance for the year 2022. This connotes that the municipal employees in Kitaotao, Bukidnon performed very well in their respective jobs, thus contributing to the attainment of LGU's priority goal of productivity.

Only "Security of Tenure" had a statistically significant positive relationship with employee performance, elaborately emphasizing the employment status; it can be deemed that most permanent might not seem bothered with problems like job security since they are already tenured compared to casual employees. Other variables, including Capability/Building/Trainings Attended, Promotion Opportunities, Hiring Process and Procedure, Healthy Working Environment, and Relationship with Co-Workers, do not show a statistically significant relationship with employee performance. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the employees' job satisfaction and their performance as municipal employees when grouped according to capability building/training attended, promotion opportunities, security of tenure, hiring process and procedure, healthy working environment, and relationship with co-workers.

There were no significant differences in their job performances when they were grouped according to age, sex, marital status, monthly salary, educational attainment, and job description.

Based on the significant findings and conclusion of this study, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

The LGU may increase its availability of funds to create plantilla positions to provide higher opportunities for career growth to employees in the non-career service, like casual employees.

There is a need to encourage further the municipal employees to continue their master's or professional studies to attain higher positions or academic rank to be qualified for higher positions and serve longer in the LGU.

The human resource office may formulate plans and implement training and seminars for newly-hired employees to increase their potential and skills to be more equipped for their job.

Realign the employee development program of the LGU to the trends and current needs of the municipal employees to yield a higher level of job satisfaction.

The LGU, through the human resource office, may identify the municipal employees who were performers in their respective offices and give awards for their exemplary performance during the annual Civil Service Month culmination.

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